

ISic0088

I.Sicily inscription 0088

Language

Latin

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. ara

2. imp(eratori) · Cae[sari]

3. et · [L]iv[iae]

4. matri [Ti(beri)Caes(aris)]

5. imp(eratoris) Cae[s][[(aris) fili]

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Manganaro 1988/1989 provides an alternative reconstruction: Ara imp(eratori)

Cae[s(ari) Aug(usto)] / et Liv[iae deae] / matri [Tib. Caes(aris)] / imp(eratoris)

Cae[s(aris) Aug(usti) f(ilii)]

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285021

EDR 109649

EDCS 22100041

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0088. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4334083>